

Development Technology Of Military Patriotic Education In The Students Of The Call For Military Education

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Abstract: *In this article, ideas are put forward about educating young students in the spirit of military patriotism. It is known to everyone that educating young people, who are the future of the state, with high moral qualities, humane, physically strong, patriotic, with military knowledge, in the spirit of national pride is the most urgent issue of today. The article can be used by representatives of relevant fields.*

Keywords — student youth, military-patriotic spirit, patriotic person, education, enlightenment, development.

INTRODUCTION.

Reforms are spreading more and more in new Uzbekistan. Dramatic changes are taking place in all aspects of our life, including the education of the young generation. Actions to restore and further enrich our history, spirituality, fundamental changes in the way of education and training of quality personnel are among these. These things are not done for nothing. Because the development of any country depends on the level of knowledge and spirituality of the people.

The main part. When we talk about patriotism, it is faith, honesty, love, consequence, passion, honor, loyalty to the motherland, to one's people, moral values, ideas, views that are ingrained in the blood of the Uzbek people. is now understood. Formation of patriotic feeling in educational institutions is the main content of education. In the formation of patriotic feelings, the state symbols of Uzbekistan, the flag, the coat of arms, the anthem, the Uzbek language, the Constitution, and other cultural and educational methods that are suitable for this nation, this land, and the feelings and qualities are transferred. is reflected in the activity. Since the issue of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is one of the issues at the state level, it is appropriate to implement the tasks set out in clearly planned roadmaps for such goals.

On the topic of patriotism, many examples of creativity of our scholars and scholars have reached us. Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Muhammad Zahiriddin Babur, Mirzo Ulug'bek and other examples of creativity of our ancestors have occupied a special place even in our time, and are used as examples and examples in the education of young people. Everyone interprets the concept of homeland in different ways, at their own level of understanding. This is the place where a person is born, where the blood of the navel is shed, where childhood and youth are spent, where he gets education, where he travels and stays.

Loving the motherland, serving for its development, protecting it from the evil eye and black forces, protecting its honor - all these are among the responsible tasks that you and we face. The concept of homeland, the feeling of loving,

honoring and protecting it can be observed not only in humans, but also in the animal world.

A fish tends to water, an animal to its nest, an insect nest. Those non-thinking creatures and insects recognize their home, build it, live in it with their partner, continue their offspring, and protect it when necessary. Therefore, this feeling should be highly developed in a person who is gifted with intelligence and thinking, who is the best of all beings in existence. In the rapidly developing period, the scope of work in our country is expanding day by day. With the efforts and initiatives of the head of our state, we are witnessing unprecedented levels of development in the life of our country. All the works and reforms carried out in the way of peaceful living of people, protection of their interests, bringing our country to the world arena, raising its reputation, in the words of the President, - to please the people, are considered as an important strategic issue in the development of our society. The content of the five priority directions of the Action Strategy for the further development of Uzbekistan includes meeting the material and spiritual needs of the people living in this country, improving their comfortable lifestyle, increasing the country's influence and reputation in the world community, and other issues. Self-sacrifice of people with a strong sense of patriotism plays an important role in the implementation of such great works. "Watan" is derived from the Arabic word, which means "motherland".

Homeland means the place where the navel blood of a person was shed, the place where his descendants and ancestors were born, his social environment and the person, his life and spiritual concepts. Patriotism means devotion to the Motherland, service to it, preservation of national peace, spiritual and moral qualities that encourage to be active for the development of the Motherland. Patriotism means loving the land inherited from our ancestors, preserving and developing the country's past and future, folk traditions, songs, and values." The issue of youth education is one of the most important strategic tasks of our state policy today. Education of young people and development of their personality in all aspects is entrusted to all general education schools. These tasks are considered to be the main factor for the development of all abilities and creative aspirations of students.

The explanation of advanced ideas, the changes that are happening in our time, as well as historical topics in a modern spirit is a rich source for educating boys and girls in ideological belief and spiritual worldview. Only then will a strong national educational system, which will have an emotional impact on the spirit of the young generation, educate courage, bravery and initiative in them. The concept of patriotism is often used in relation to military activities. In one respect, this is true. However, if we apply this sentiment only to the military, we will be using a narrow sense of patriotism. It is desirable to see patriotism in all activities. The concept of homeland can be used in broad and narrow senses.

Broad definition: Motherland is the area where representatives of a nation live together, where their ancestors have lived since time immemorial, and in the narrow sense it means the house, neighborhood, village where a person was born and raised. In our people, when it is said that such and such person became a citizen, it is probably said from this point of view that that person has a home and a shelter. Alisher Navoi, a great thinker, enlightener and great poet of the Uzbek people, paid special attention to the work of educating young people. He encouraged young people to love science and their homeland, and emphasized the need to use the learned science and craft for the sake of the people and the homeland.

In Navoi's work, the concept of Motherland is used in a wide sense. In one definition, he applied the word "Homeland" in a geographical sense, i.e., the place where he was born and grew up. For example, in a poetic letter written to the master poet Sayyid Hasan Ardasher: "Being in one's country was a burden, and the heart was suffering from suffering" - he mentioned his hometown Herat.

As Ustad Maqsud Shayhzade said, there are views that Navoi felt "abroad" even when he went to the distant regions of the Khurasan kingdom. Navoi lived mainly in Herat and Mashhad until 1465-66. As it can be seen from the word "ghurbat" in the poem, there are also assumptions that he wrote this poem not in his native Herat, but in a foreign country, that is, in Mashhad. The years he spent in Mashhad, far from his native city of Herat and his relatives, must have been very difficult, - says Professor Abduqadir Hayitmetov, - he remembered those years in "Majolisun Nafois" and described himself as a "stranger". and says that when he got sick, he "fell somewhere".

We can find a lot of views related to the education and upbringing of the young generation in the life and creative work of Alisher Navoi. It is known that Navoi, both as a creator and as an official, was an unceasing and tireless initiative in creating practical conditions for maintaining peace and encouraging young people to learn. He widely promoted these ideas in his works. It is necessary to widely apply the content and essence of the ideas in Navoi's works, the activities promoted and implemented in his time in the activities related to the education of the young generation today. It is necessary to consider the general issues regarding the practical application of forms of education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit.

Education of young people in the military patriotic spirit is mainly carried out in four stages: The first stage (ages 3-7) is considered to be the stage where the first ideas about the surrounding world and the Motherland appear, in which children are taught various poems, tunes and songs, cartoons and various lessons in the family and preschool educational institutions. It includes understanding the world through playing games, drawing pictures, forming love for the motherland based on getting to know state symbols (flag, coat of arms, anthem). In the second stage (children aged 7-16), strengthening students' love and loyalty to the Motherland, increasing their enthusiasm for military service and fulfilling their filial duty to the motherland with high responsibility, strengthening their positive thoughts towards our Armed Forces, He is encouraged to do good deeds, such as forming a person who is physically healthy, strong and strong-willed, mentally mature, broad-minded, independent thinking. The third stage (adolescents aged 16-18) is aimed at ensuring mental and physical readiness of young people to serve the Motherland and its protection. The fourth stage (ages 18-30) involves improving the physical and spiritual abilities, leadership skills and intellectual potential, general and professional skills of young people, encouraging them to regularly work on themselves, lead a healthy life and achieve this. holds The concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is developed on the basis of the main principles and priorities of the state policy on youth implemented in the country.

Relevant tasks and ways to solve them, determines the role and importance of state and non-state organizations, family, neighborhood, educational institutions, mutual cooperation in this regard, taking into account national and international legal norms. All the work, material and moral support, and the attention paid to young people will definitely show results.

Summary. It can be concluded from the above that our main goal is to inculcate the ideas of patriotism, humanity and truthfulness in our youth, who are the future of New Uzbekistan. These ideas form the basis of moral education. Therefore, it is more important than ever to form and expand the moral knowledge of our young people at every stage of educational institutions.

In addition, by forming a media culture in our youth, we should educate them in moral knowledge so that they can use social networks wisely. we need to enrich the prosperity of Education of a generation with a high moral and intellectual potential is disappearing as one of the most important tasks not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole world. The future of the country will be determined by the morally perfect generation. Spiritual perfection is the most important factor of the development of the society.

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